

RegTech – Use of Blockchain Technology in AML Compliance

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Keywords:

1. Introduction

Blockchain technology provides disintermediation and transparency using distributed ledger technology (DLT). This enables unique cost-saving opportunities in the blockchain space to shore up operational efficiencies in monitoring for AML (Anti-Money Laundering) regulatory compliance and enforcement.

2. Aim

To evaluate and discuss the use, merits and limitations of blockchain technology in providing significant cost savings for regulated financial institutions including banks, credit unions, asset managers, and money service businesses.

3. Materials and Methods

A PowerPoint presentation (length dependent on time available for the presentation and/or panel) to provide the context and visual backdrop. Various business case studies will be examined to support the user case stemming from clients that we've advised in the financial institution space in the area of AML regulatory compliance.

4. Results

Although blockchain is a new and emerging technology, we can use existing business case studies to show operational inefficiencies and how they can be reduced while enhancing accuracy rates. This can generate more accurate screening, data mining and analytics, enhanced trust, faster delivery, lower compliance monitoring costs, and improved customer and compliance staff experience. Other wider enterprise-wide and industry benefits include but are not limited to, aggregating and automating immutable data to streamline feeds for regulators and other stakeholders. Some regulators still use paper-based forms via PDF to collect KYC information from their registrants, an inefficient and costly means of tracking and monitoring data. The use of DLT will improve the speed and quality of regulatory review since the need for reconciliation is eliminated.

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5. Conclusions

Blockchain technology will yield significant operational cost savings in the area of AML regulatory compliance and enforcement. It will reduce manual labor costs, error rates, and false positives across the AML regulatory spectrum.

6. Key Words

Blockchain technology, AML, Anti-Money Laundering (AML), Regulatory Compliance, Counter-Terrorist Financing (CTF), FinCEN, FINTRAC, AML Regulatory Compliance, Regulatory enforcement, compliance enforcement, blockchain applications in compliance

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